

Safe optimal vessel planning on natural inland waterways

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Abstract

Despite inland ports play an essential role in today's global logistics chain, many problems still remain unsolved. One of the main challenges that inland waterways face is the trip planning of cargo vessels. A correct trip planning does not only improve the efficiency and prestige of the port, but is also crucial to ensure the safety of operations. This issue is particularly critical in the case of natural waterways whose depth and width are conditioned by natural phenomena that, in principle, cannot be controlled. This is the case of the Guadalquivir river, a waterway that connects the Atlantic Ocean and the inland Port of Seville in the south of Spain. In this context, this work proposes a two-step solution to optimize the time needed for vessels to complete their journey through the waterway while considering the constraint imposed by the time-varying depth and encountering situations. The outcome is the set of times when vessels are required to cross a series of boundaries delimiting the different sections of the waterway. The advantages of the proposed approach are studied in contrast to a first-arrived first-served scheduling solution in terms of optimality and feasibility.

Planning, MILP, inland waterways, safe navigation.

1 Introduction

In the consumer society we live in, maritime transport is one of the sectors with a greater impact on countries' development and the growth of global economy [1]. As it has been demonstrated [26], the pace of growth of a country's economy is directly and highly correlated with the amount of investment on logistic infrastructures and the improvement of maritime transport. Thus, it is of

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utmost importance to design a road map to adapt existing port systems to meet the requirements of today's society. This requires not only the modernization of port facilities and the use of new technologies [12], but also the development of more efficient management strategies to improve the efficiency of the overall logistic process [17].

Many research lines have focused on improving the efficiency of different port operations. This is the case of the berth allocation problem (BAP) [3, 9, 10, 22], which deals with optimizing berthing times, or the quay crane scheduling problem (QCSP), which aims at scheduling quay cranes for loading and unloading containers in such a way that vessels' turnaround times are minimized [4, 20, 23, 29, 34].

In addition, in inland ports connected to the sea coast through some channel or waterway, as in the case of the Port of Seville, the navigation-oriented trip planning of vessels plays a key role in port efficiency. This problem does not only need to consider matters relating to vessels' characteristics, but also different exogenous factors that may affect the waterway, such as the effect of the tide on the depth. Various studies have addressed this problem. For example, in [32], a sequential algorithm based on priority is proposed for a two-way waterway. In [30] and [21], a genetic algorithm and a method based on fuzzy logic, respectively, are employed to solve the problem of planning vessels in different inland waterways. In [33], the vessel scheduling problem and the berth allocation problem are jointly solved.

Other research lines have focused on solving all the different problems affecting the traffic scheduling problem for some particular waterway to provide a global solution. This is the case of the works developed in [19] and [13], where authors propose a mathematical formulation for optimizing navigation channel traffic while minimizing anchorage area utilization. Based on these works, in [16], authors manage the vessel traffic problem by optimizing the utilization of the navigation channel and anchoring areas while introducing as decision variable the utilization of port pilots with the objective of minimizing not only berthing times but also the pilot dispatching cost, considering tidal windows to access and sail through the channel. This approach integrates the vessel traffic management problem with pilot planning problem, which is extensively detailed in [31]. This work is complemented by the work developed in [14], where a problem for scheduling tugboats for mooring and unmooring operations in busy seaports is proposed. In the same vein, in [15], authors propose an scheduling problem that aims at addressing inter-shipping line equity in the navigation channel of a seaport while trying to find the best compromise between two conflicting objectives, equity and efficiency, again considering tidal windows to access and sail through the channel.

However, regardless of the great interest that this problem has raised, there are few works focusing on natural waterways whose depth depends on the irregular bathymetric profile of the waterway and the tidal effect, which complicates the problem including dynamic constraints. Regarding this issue, a mixed-integer linear program (MILP) is proposed in [18] to schedule vessels sailing through a multiple channel waterway subject to the effect of the tide. The au-

thors present a heuristic method to solve the planning problem —proven to be NP-hard— within a reasonable computational time. Another work dealing with waterways under the effect of the tide is [24], where the planning problem in the Guadalquivir waterway is solved using a three-step methodology. First, all possible routes are calculated according to depth constraints, then the trip plans of all vessels are obtained optimizing some performance criteria, and finally, the trip plans are modified manually to take into account encountering situations with other vessels.

Most formulations of the scheduling problem in artificial or natural waterways affected by natural phenomena do not consider the effect of time-changing depth at each location of the waterway but rather focus on finding tidal windows to access or leaving the channel. In the present work, we propose a more general formulation of the planning and scheduling problem in inland waterways while ensuring the existence of a feasible trajectory considering all the different natural and operational constraints affecting navigation in this type of waterways. A two-step solution is proposed. In the first step, a series of tubes (collection of time windows) that ensure the existence of a feasible solution are found. In the second step, a planning problem is proposed, where we take as decision variables the times when each vessel crosses a series of waypoints contained in the tubes found in the previous step. We take as example the case of the Guadalquivir river, where navigation is hampered by its location in a highly protected natural area. This affects the overall management of the Port of Seville, which is the main intermodal logistic node connecting the Canary Islands to the rest of Spain [25]. Because of the impossibility of carrying out almost any adaptation work in such a vulnerable area, the only way of expanding the capacity of the waterway is by improving the management of vessels, something that requires adopting new technologies and managing strategies in the context of smart ports and industry 4.0 [7]. The objective is to find, for a given set of vessels arriving at both extremes of the waterway, the optimal trip plans that minimize some performance criteria that depends on the time vessels spend waiting and navigating through the waterway while satisfying a series of operational constraints. For each vessel, its optimal trip plan is a series of times when each vessel should cross a series of boundaries that divide the waterway into different sections, minimizing some performance index and ensuring that, for any vessel adhering to its optimal trip plan, there exists at least one feasible trajectory that satisfies all operational constraints.

We show that the proposed two-step solution can be implemented using off-the-shelf solvers in real time for a number of vessels much higher than the current demands of the Port of Seville. In addition, we demonstrate that it also outperforms a commonly employed solution in which the trip plans of the vessels are planned by means of a first-arrived first-served policy. This policy not only leads to suboptimal decisions, but also increments the probability of suffering an accident due to the human component in the process [5].

It is important to remark that the objective of this work is not to control vessels' motion in the waterway, but to develop a planning tool to provide a set of indicative times when each vessel should cross each boundary in the waterway.

Figure 1: Guadalquivir waterway.

Thus, the problem of vessels' motion control is not addressed in this work, and it is assumed that it is the pilot's responsibility to control the vessel and adhere to the provided trip plan.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we provide a brief description of the Guadalquivir waterway planning problem and the proposed two-step solution. This solution is described in detail in Sections III and IV. In Section 5, we present simulation results for different scenarios in the Guadalquivir waterway. Finally, in Section 6, the main conclusions of this work are summarized.

2 Vessel planning in the Guadalquivir waterway

The Atlantic Ocean and the inland Port of Seville, in the south of Spain, are connected by an 87 *km* natural waterway (see Figure 1) of variable depth and width, the Guadalquivir waterway, which crosses the highly protected environment of Doñana Natural Park. This fact makes it difficult to address many of the problems associated to the different natural effects that affect navigation in this waterway, such as the tide, the bathymetric profile, and the variable width of the waterway. In addition, river pilots —which are a scarce resource— are needed to sail through the waterway, being the Port of Seville the authority in charge of assigning a different pilot to each vessel.

Figure 2: Prediction of the depth of the Guadalquivir waterway for the week considered.

In this work we focus on planning the trips of the vessels according to the demands of the port authorities. Navigation issues are assumed to be handled by the vessel pilots in order to follow the trip plan. One of the main difficulties when planning the trips of the vessels through a natural waterway is the irregular bathymetric profile because it restricts their maximum allowable draught. In the case of the Guadalquivir river, due to the regulatory measures for the conservation of the area where the waterway is located, dredging operations are not allowed [8], something that would greatly simplify the planning problem. The bathymetric profile of the Guadalquivir can be found in [6], where it was obtained by making use of a multibeam echo sounder.

The other critical natural factor that influences navigation in the waterway is the effect of the tide. To obtain a map of the tide for a period of one week, we use predictions obtained using the first principle models developed in [28]. Combining these predictions with the bathymetric profile, the map shown in Figure 2 has been obtained. Note that this map is a graphical representation of a matrix \mathcal{D} whose elements $d_{m,n}$ provide the depth of the waterway at time m in location n . The number of rows and columns of \mathcal{D} depend on the time-space discretization employed (one value every 6 minutes ($1/10 h$) and every 100 meters ($1/10 km$)). This map will be employed to carry out all the experiments presented in Section 5.

Using the map represented in Figure 2, it is possible to find, for a given vessel, the time-space points in which it can sail taking into account its draught. The map depicted in Figure 3 has been obtained for vessels with a draught of 7.5 meters, where the dark blue zones represent those regions to be avoided by the

Figure 3: Map of time-space points in which a 7.5 m draught vessel may sail for the week considered.

vessels in order to prevent a grounding accident.

Besides the constraints imposed by the time-varying depth of the waterway, it is important to guarantee safe encountering situations among vessels, i.e., it must be ensured that the sum of beams of any two vessels undergoing an encountering situation fits to the width of the channel at the point where the maneuver occurs while following the international regulations for preventing collisions [27].

A feasible trip plan for a set of vessels adapts the sailing speed of the vessels in such a way that shallow sections are crossed during high tide windows and that head-on and overtaking encounters occur in wide sections. Currently, in the port of Seville, the trip plans are obtained manually. The trip plans are sent to the vessel pilots. Calculating the trip plans is time consuming and may lead to non-optimal trip plans. The objective of the proposed scheduling algorithm is to solve this problem automatically minimizing waiting and sailing times while reducing the risk of accident due to human errors.

2.1 Proposed two-step solution

The objective is to find the optimal trip plans for a set of N vessels that have to cross a natural waterway. We do not consider anchorage areas inside the waterway. Each of these vessels is characterized by its beam $b(i)$, its maximum speed $v(i)$, its draught $\delta(i)$, and the time when they arrive to the waterway t_i^{ready} , where the integer $i \in \mathcal{I} = \mathbf{N}_1^N = \{1, \dots, N\}$ denotes the index of the

vessel. The set \mathcal{I}_u includes all vessels sailing upstream, while the set \mathcal{I}_d includes all vessels travelling downstream. Thus, $\mathcal{I} = \mathcal{I}_u \cup \mathcal{I}_d$.

We assume there is an anchoring area at each extreme of the waterway in which vessels can wait until they are scheduled to enter the waterway. One possible option to solve the planning problem is to decide the speed of each vessel using a time-space discretisation. However, this approach leads, in general, to highly complex problems. To overcome this issue, in the proposed solution we take as decision variables the times in which each vessel crosses a series of boundaries. To this end, we consider that the waterway is divided into Z sections, where the first section corresponds to the river estuary and the last one to the entry lock of the Port of Seville. Each section $p \in \mathbf{N}_1^Z$ is characterized by its length, $d(p)$, by the maximum speed at which vessels can sail through it, $\mu(p)$, and by the practical width of the section, $w(p)$. Because of safety reasons, the sum of the beams of any two vessels undergoing an encountering situation is limited by the practical width of the section.

The trip plan of each of the vessels is defined by the times in which the vessel must cross each of the boundaries between the different sections, including both extremes of the waterway, $p = 0$ and $p = Z$, respectively. With a slight abuse of notation, we denote these times as $t_{i,p}$, where in this case $p \in \mathbf{N}_0^Z$ denotes the northernmost boundary of section p including both extremes of the waterway located in the river estuary and the entry lock of the Port of Seville, which are boundaries $p = 0$ and $p = Z$, respectively. The sequence of times $t_{i,p}$ is increasing in p when a vessel sails upstream and decreasing in p when a vessel sails downstream. With this choice of the decision variables, all constraints considered can be modelled in an efficient way as presented in the following sections. Knowledge of these times and the length of each of the sections allows river pilots to estimate the speed at which vessels should sail through each of the sections to meet the optimal plan.

To solve this problem, we propose a two-step approach. First we calculate the sets of time windows in which each vessel is allowed to cross each of the boundaries of the waterway given their arrival times and the maximum trip duration. An algorithm is presented to calculate these sets for a single vessel, in a way such that for any travel plan that lies inside one of these sets, it is always possible to cross the waterway satisfying both the time-varying depth constraint, given by the irregular bathymetric profile and the prediction of the tide, and the maximum speed constraint.

Once these sets are computed for all vessels, a mixed-integer linear program is proposed to decide the optimal trip plans for all vessels taking into account the variable width of the waterway. This restricts the sections of the channel where encountering situations can occur according to the beam of the vessels and the width of the waterway. As an additional operation constraint, vessels must complete their trip in less than D_L hours from their arrival to the waterway at t_i^{ready} . Limiting the length of the trip to D_L is an indirect way of limiting the minimum speed of the vessels. Also, it is assumed that encountering situations are handled following the international regulations for preventing collisions at sea [27] by the river pilots and that encountering situations do not affect the

mean sailing speed of the vessels.

In the proposed solution we do not consider the length of the vessels in the crossing times. To take into account this issue, we consider an additional constraint on the crossing times at each boundary. That is, a time gap Δ_0 between two vessels crossing the same boundary is included in the planning problem.

Remark 1. *Note that, because the objective of this work is not to control vessels' motion but to develop a tool for scheduling vessels in natural waterways and provide an indicative safe crossing time through each boundary, nautical effects such as bank effect, shallow water effect, and vessel squat effect are not considered in this work since they do not affect the scheduling. In most scheduling works published so far, these effects are not considered since they just affect motion control, which in this paper is assumed to be pilot's responsibility.*

3 Safe tube calculation

To prevent grounding accidents, it is crucial to ensure that vessels are always located at time-space points where the depth of the waterway is greater than the draught of the vessels. Taking into account the time-varying depth of the waterway is a challenging task. To solve the planning problem, for each vessel i considered, we assume that there exists a set $\mathcal{K}(i)$ of safe tubes. These safe tubes are regions in the time-space map that connect both extremes of the waterway, providing trip plans that satisfy depth and speed constraints. Each tube $k \in \mathcal{K}(i)$ is defined by the minimum and maximum times, $t_{i,k,p}^{min}$ and $t_{i,k,p}^{max}$ in which vessel i has to cross each boundary p . Without loss of generality, we present next an algorithm that computes all the possible safe tubes corresponding to a given vessel travelling upstream. For vessels travelling downstream the procedure is equivalent.

Given the arrival time of vessel $i \in \mathcal{I}_u$ to the waterway, t_i^{ready} , and the maximum period of time we allow this vessel to spend sailing through the waterway, D_L , we first calculate, for each boundary $p \in \mathbf{N}_0^Z$ the set Q_p as the union of all possible time windows in which vessel i can cross boundary p between t_i^{ready} and $t_i^{ready} + D_L$; that is, the time intervals in which the depth of the waterway at the boundary considered, taking into account both the bathymetric profile and the tide, is enough for this vessel to cross safely. In general, Q_p is defined as the union of several disjoint time intervals denoted as Q_p^l with $l \in \mathbf{N}_1^{card(Q_p)}$.

In Figure 3, the set of time windows in which vessels with a draught equal to 7.5 meters can cross through each of the boundaries is given by the intersection of each boundary with the yellow areas.

Figure 4 shows an illustrative example of a waterway divided into a total of three sections in which the vertical axis represents time and the horizontal axis represents space. In the figure, the boxes at the boundaries show the time intervals in which depth constraint is satisfied. The intervals shadowed in green

Figure 4: Admissible time windows Q_p of an example of a three-section waterway.

represent those time windows that can be considered to build the set of safe tubes.

Once the set of admissible time windows has been found for each boundary p , we could in principle calculate the set of safe tubes as causal combinations of these windows. However, the number of possible safe tubes would grow exponentially with the number of sections. Figure 7 shows the tree obtained for all possible sequences of time intervals in each of the four boundaries. The resulting tree has one depth level for each boundary. Note that the number of possible sequences that reach boundary 3 from boundary 0 grows exponentially. In this particular example, there are 18 ($1 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 \cdot 2$) possible sequences. In general, this approach cannot be used. In addition, while any of these combinations would guarantee that depth constraints are not violated at the different boundaries of the waterway, there is no certainty about what may happen while crossing each section taking into account depth constraints and speed limits. To solve this problem, we introduce the concept of safe region between two time windows belonging to consecutive boundaries and propose an algorithm that explores all the possible combinations of time windows.

Definition 3.1. A safe region connecting two time windows is a region in the time space map for which it is possible to find at least one feasible inner trajectory that does not violate neither depth nor speed constraints.

In figure 5, an example of safe region defined at section p , N_p^r , is displayed.

The region is a trapezoid defined by four vertexes, A , B , C and D . In the figure, the dashed black lines represent trajectories described by vessels sailing at the highest allowed speed in the section, $\bar{\mu}_i(p)$, which is given by the minimum between the maximum speed allowed in section p , $\mu(p)$, and the maximum speed of vessel i , $v(i)$. Vertical lines correspond to a speed equal to zero, which implies that going from point A to point B (or from C to D) can be achieved by simply stopping the vessel at the corresponding boundary. Point A provides a bound on the earliest time (t_p^{entry}) when the vessel can cross safely the exit time window of the safe region defined in the previous section, N_{p-1}^k . Arriving earlier would imply abandoning the previous safe region N_{p-1}^k . Point B provides the latest time (t_p^{latest}) when the vessel can reach the exit time window of N_{p-1}^k . Arriving later at the left boundary would imply that the depth constraint would be violated, even if the vessel travels at the highest allowed speed (see the dashed line crossing through point B). If the vessel arrives at the boundary in the time interval $[t_p^{entry}, t_p^{latest}]$, then there exists at least one possible trip plan that can be followed without violating depth and speed constraints. Point C and D provide the earliest and latest time at which the vessel could safely get to the next border Q_p^l .

Different programming approaches can be adopted to obtain vertexes A , B , C and D that define the safe region N_p^r . In the results presented in the simulation section, point C is obtained by computing the highest point in boundary Q_p^l that can be reached from the left safe region N_{p-1}^k travelling at the highest allowed speed $\bar{\mu}_i(p)$, and without violating the depth constraints (i.e. hitting the dark blue region). Notice that the slope of the dashed lines in the figure corresponds to the trajectory described by a vessel travelling at speed $\bar{\mu}_i(p)$. Similarly, point B is obtained by determining the lowest point on the left boundary, and belonging to the exit time window of the previous safe region, that can be connected with the right time window Q_p^l , sailing at speed $\bar{\mu}_i(p)$, and without hitting the depth constraints. Point A is the highest point of the left boundary belonging to the previous safe region N_{p-1}^k . Finally, point D is the lowest point on the border Q_p^l that does not violate depth constraints. This procedure has to account for the time-space discretization of the predicted depth map \mathcal{D} .

We notice that there might be situations in which it is not possible to reach Q_p^l , starting from the previous safe region N_{p-1}^k , without violating either depth or speed constraints. In this case, the corresponding safe region does not exist. The proposed procedure to obtain each safe region is summarized in Algorithm 1.

The objective is to build the safe tubes to safely cross the waterway by recursively linking together safe regions between consecutive sections. To do that, we follow a procedure that can be represented as a tree building algorithm. At each iteration of this procedure, we try to concatenate the safe regions found in the previous iteration for the previous section p of the waterway with the the safe crossing windows defined at the next boundary of the waterway. At each iteration of the tree building algorithm, given the exit time window of N_{p-1}^k , and the time window to be reached, Q_p^l , it is necessary to find, if it exists, the

Figure 5: Example of computing of a safe crossing region N_p^r connecting the previous one N_{p-1}^k to the border Q_p^l .

Algorithm 1

Require: $N_{p-1}^k, Q_p^l, \mu(p), d(p), i, v(i), \mathcal{D}$

- 1: $\bar{\mu}_i(p) = \min\{\mu(p), v(i)\}$.
 - 2: Find the earliest time $t_p^{earliest} \in Q_p^l$ when vessel i can exit safely section p starting from the exit time window of N_{p-1}^k . This time is obtained computing the highest point in Q_p^l that can be connected with the exit time window of N_{p-1}^k with a line of slope $\bar{\mu}_i(p)$ that does not violate depth constraints given by depth map \mathcal{D} .
 - 3: Find the latest time $t_p^{latest} \in N_{p-1}^k$ when vessel i can enter safely section p exiting through Q_p^l . This is obtained computing the lowest point in the exit time window of N_{p-1}^k that can be connected with Q_p^l with a line of slope $\bar{\mu}_i(p)$ that does not violate depth constraints given by depth map \mathcal{D} .
 - 4: If these times exist, then define N_p^r as the trapezoid given by vertexes $A, B, C,$ and $D,$ with C corresponding to $t_p^{earliest}$, B to t_p^{latest} , A to the highest point of the exit time window of N_{p-1}^k (t_p^{entry}), and D to the lowest point of Q_p^l (t_p^{exit}).
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Figure 6: Safe tube tree building algorithm for vessels travelling upstream.

Figure 7: Safe tube tree for the three section example waterway.

corresponding safe region connecting both time intervals. If this is the case, a new node is added to the tree. This procedure is summarized in the flow diagram depicted in Figure 6.

In Figure 7, the resulting tree is shown in green for the waterway considered in Figure 4. In this figure, each labeled node represents a safe crossing region to cross the waterway safely up to the section represented by the level of the tree. Unlabelled nodes indicate that it is not possible to reach the next time interval departing from the previous safe region and would not have to be further explored. For example, we assume that it is not possible to reach Q_3^1 from N_2^1 , which implies that it is not possible to reach Q_3^1 following the sequence $Q_0^1-Q_1^1-Q_2^1-Q_3^1$. In this example, it is not possible to reach neither Q_2^2 from N_1^2 nor Q_2^3 from N_2^3 , leading to only two possible safe tubes defined by the two children nodes of the tree, N_3^1 and N_3^2 .

The set of safe tubes for some vessel i , $\mathcal{K}(i)$, is obtained from the leaf nodes of the tree. Given any of the leaf nodes, k , and the crossing interval at each boundary p , i.e., the values of $t_{i,k,p}^{min}$ and $t_{i,k,p}^{max}$, are defined by the entry times of the parent node at level p of the resulting tree, except for the time window at boundary Z which is defined by the exit time window of the leaf node.

Remark 2. *In the proposed algorithm, it is supposed that there are river pilots in charge of controlling the speed of vessels to meet the optimal plan without violating the depth constraint.*

Remark 3. *It could be the case that the division in sections of the river is such that there might appear closed regions in the depth map that are not intersected by any boundary. In that case, the algorithm has to be modified to take this issue into account and, as shown in Figure 8, the number of resulting safe crossing regions for each section would increase proportionally to the number of closed*

regions not intersected by any boundary. In the example shown in the figure, given the exit time window of the parent node N_p^k and the time interval to be reached, Q_p^l , two different nodes would be generated and added to the tree.

Figure 8: Example of tubes in the case of existence of a closed region in the depth map that is not intersected by any boundary.

4 Optimal vessel planning

Once the safe tubes are found, the planning problem can be solved. To this end, we present a formulation which takes the form of a mixed-integer linear problem (MILP) integrating logic and dynamic constraints [2]. In what follows we present the cost function, constraints and auxiliary decision variables to model the problem considered.

4.1 Cost function

The objective of the proposed formulation is to minimize the time vessels need to complete their trips along the waterway (navigation cost) and the time vessels spend waiting in the anchorage zone before they are given permission to enter the waterway (waiting cost). The time when each vessel i is ready to begin its trip is given by t_i^{ready} . Thus, the performance index to be optimized is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
J = & \alpha \cdot \left[\underbrace{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} (t_{i,Z} - t_{i,0}) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_d} (t_{i,0} - t_{i,Z})}_{\text{Navigation cost}(C_N)} \right] \\
& + \beta \cdot \left[\underbrace{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} (t_{i,0} - t_i^{ready}) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_d} (t_{i,Z} - t_i^{ready})}_{\text{Waiting cost}(C_W)} \right], \tag{1}
\end{aligned}$$

where α and β can be chosen to weight differently navigation and waiting costs.

4.2 Speed constraint

In each section of the waterway, there is a maximum speed that vessels can not exceed given by $\bar{\mu}_i(p)$. This speed determines the minimum period of time needed for any vessel to sail through section p .

To model this issue, for each section $p \in \mathbf{N}_1^Z$, and for each vessel $i \in \mathcal{I}_u$, the following constraints are included

$$(t_{i,p} - t_{i,p-1}) \cdot \bar{\mu}_i(p) \geq d(p), \tag{2}$$

$$t_{i,0} \geq t_i^{ready}. \tag{3}$$

In addition, for each section $p \in \mathbf{N}_1^Z$ and for each vessel $i \in \mathcal{I}_d$ the following constraints are included

$$(t_{i,p-1} - t_{i,p}) \cdot \bar{\mu}_i(p) \geq d(p), \tag{4}$$

$$t_{i,Z} \geq t_i^{ready}. \tag{5}$$

4.3 Safe tube selection

To select the safe tube in which vessel $i \in \mathcal{I}$ sails among the ones found using the algorithm presented in the previous section, $\mathcal{K}(i)$, a set of binary decision variables $r_{i,k}$ is considered, with $k \in \mathcal{K}(i)$. If $r_{i,k}$ takes value 1, then the trip of vessel i must be contained inside tube k . The rest of the variables corresponding to other safe tubes must take value zero. To this end, for each vessel i and for each $p \in \mathbf{N}_0^Z$ the following set of constraints is considered

$$t_{i,p} \leq t_{i,k,p}^{max} + M \cdot (1 - r_{i,k}), \tag{6}$$

$$t_{i,p} \geq t_{i,k,p}^{min} - M \cdot (1 - r_{i,k}), \tag{7}$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}(i)} r_{i,k} = 1. \tag{8}$$

4.4 Encountering situations constraint

Finally, it is important to guarantee that encountering situations between vessels, both overtaking and head-on maneuvers, occur at points with a practical width greater than the sum of the beams of the vessels involved. To this end, for each pair of vessels i and j with $i, j \in \mathcal{I}$ and $i < j$ a binary decision variable $c_{i,j,p}$ is included for each boundary $p \in \mathbf{N}_0^Z$ in the optimization problem. This variable is equal to one if both vessels encounter head-on or overtake each other in section p . The value of the variables corresponding to forbidden manoeuvres is set to zero; that is

$$c_{i,j,p} = 0 \quad \forall i, j, p \text{ such that } b(i) + b(j) > w(p). \quad (9)$$

We assume that each vessel i arrives at all boundaries of the waterway before vessel $j > i$ up to the boundary p in which $c_{i,j,p}$ takes value 1. After this event, vessel j arrives at the following boundaries before vessel i . If the values of these variables for all sections p are equal to zero or if $c_{i,j,0} = 1$, vessels never encounter each other. In addition, a minimum time gap Δ_0 between two vessels crossing the same boundary is considered.

To model these issues the following constraints are included in the optimization problem:

$$t_{i,p} + \Delta_0 \leq t_{j,p} + M \cdot \sum_{l \in \mathbf{N}_0^p} c_{i,j,l}, \quad (10)$$

$$t_{j,p} + \Delta_0 \leq t_{i,p} + M \cdot \left(1 - \sum_{l \in \mathbf{N}_0^p} c_{i,j,l} \right), \quad (11)$$

where M is a number significantly larger than the value of $t_{i,p}$ and Δ_0 is the minimum time difference between the crossing times of both vessels.

To guarantee that each pair of vessels i, j can only encounter each other once during their trip, the following constraint is included

$$\sum_{p \in \mathbf{N}_0^Z} c_{i,j,p} \leq 1. \quad (12)$$

In Figure 9, all possible encountering scenarios for two vessels sailing in opposite directions are shown for a simple example of a waterway divided into three sections. In this figure, the horizontal axis represents the distance between both extremes of the waterway. The boundaries of the sections are shown in continuous blue lines. The vertical axis represents time, being the initial time of the scheduling at the top of the figure. Vessel trajectories are represented by dashed black and green lines with encounters highlighted by red stars. For vessels travelling in the same direction, a similar figure can be drawn. In the left of the figure, the corresponding value of the binary variables for each scenario is shown.

Figure 9: Example of all possible values $c_{i,j,p}$ can take for a 3 section waterway.

Remark 4. *The encountering situations constraint can be modified to allow several overtaking or head-on maneuvers among two vessels. This option is not taken into account in this work.*

Remark 5. *It is assumed that vessels undergoing any encountering situation do not change their speed during the maneuver.*

4.5 Optimization problem

Using the previously described constraints, (2) to (12), the optimization problem proposed to find the optimal values of the decision variables that define the optimal sailing plan, t^* , c^* and r^* can be formulated as

$$t^*, c^*, r^* = \arg \min_{t, c, r} J \quad \text{s.t (2) - (12)}. \quad (13)$$

In the proposed optimization problem, we assume that the objective is to decide the trip plans for all vessels considered. However it is also possible to consider vessels with trip plans that cannot be modified. This allows to address different scenarios that arise in normal operation conditions, such as including a newly arrived vessel to a waterway in which there are vessels already sailing or even when rescheduling is needed due to unexpected events. Also note that the arrival time of any vessel could be imposed by adding a new constraint that fixes the value of $t_{i,Z}$ or $t_{i,0}$ to the desired time for vessels travelling upstream and downstream, respectively.

Remark 6. *The proposed procedure is based on an NP-hard optimization problem, and hence, it may not be appropriate for a high number of vessels or waterway sections. In the simulation section we demonstrate that the proposed solution can be applied to the current demands of the Port of Seville. The complexity of the optimization problem depends mainly on the number of vessels N , the number of sections Z and the number of safe tubes for each ship. In particular, the number of constraints and binary variables grow with the square of N and linearly with Z and the number of tubes.*

5 Simulation results

In this section, we apply the proposed trip planning method to the case of the Guadalquivir river. To validate the proposed approach, a series of randomly generated scenarios are considered. All optimization problems have been solved using Gurobi solver [11]. The simulations have been carried out on an AMD Ryzen 5 platform working at 3 GHz.

5.1 Model parameters

The Guadalquivir river is divided into a total of $Z = 24$ sections, and hence, there are a total of 25 boundaries. Each of these sections p is characterised by its

Table 1: Guadalquivir waterway parameters.

id	$d(km)$	$\mu(km/h)$	w	id	$d(km)$	$\mu(km/h)$	w
1	1.9	10.1860	1	13	4.2	19.4460	8
2	1.4	16.6680	4	14	4.5	19.4460	1
3	4.5	16.6680	2	15	3.5	22.2240	8
4	4.2	17.5940	4	16	1.2	18.5200	4
5	2.0	17.5940	4	17	3.4	21.2980	4
6	5.2	18.5200	4	18	1.7	23.1500	4
7	6.6	21.2980	4	19	2.0	23.1500	4
8	3.5	21.2980	4	20	4.2	23.1500	4
9	5.9	21.2980	2	21	3.0	22.2240	1
10	5.4	22.2240	4	22	2.2	18.5200	8
11	2.1	22.2240	4	23	4.8	21.2980	1
12	4.7	22.2240	1	24	4.9	21.2980	2

length $d(p)$, the maximum speed at which vessels can sail through it $\mu(p)$, and its width $w(p)$, whose values are detailed in Table I ¹. The beams of the vessels are categorised in three categories, namely small, medium and large, which are quantified as 1, 2 and 4, respectively. The width of each section, rather than its real measure, receives a value contained in the discrete set $\{2, 4, 8\}$. Only vessels whose sum of beams is less than or equal to the width of the waterway can encounter in that section.

In all the simulations carried out in this section, the objective is to minimize the total trip time of all vessels considered, and hence, the weights α and β are both set to 1. In addition, we consider a minimum time between crossings of $\Delta_0 = 1 h/10$.

5.2 Scenario generation

In order to analyse the performance of the proposed approach, it has been applied to a number of different randomly generated scheduling scenarios. Each scenario is defined by the following parameters:

- N : number of vessels considered, half of them sailing upstream and the other half sailing downstream.
- t^{init} : Initial time of the scenario.
- λ : Characteristic parameter of a Poisson distribution used to define the time interval between two consecutive arrivals of vessels to the same end of the waterway.
- D_L : Maximum period of time a vessel is allowed to be sailing before reaching its final destination.

¹All data employed to generate the different scenarios are provided by the local authorities with slight modifications for confidential matters.

Table 2: Safe tube computing time as a function of D_L

D_L [$h/10$]	100	120	140	160	180	200
Comp. time (s)	1.48	1.78	2.14	2.57	3.25	4.22

Figure 10: Number of binary variables, constraints and safe tubes as a function of N .

Each scenario generated using these parameters is defined by the sequence of times in which vessels arrive to the waterway. The sequence at each end of the waterway is obtained following a Poisson distribution with characteristic parameter λ , starting both sequences at time t^{init} . The width of each vessel is determined randomly following an uniform distribution. We assume that all vessels have a draught equal to 7.5 meters, which approximately corresponds to the draught of the largest vessel currently operating in the Port of Seville, to account for the worst case scenario.

5.3 Simulation results

In this subsection, we show the simulations carried out to test the proposed approach and analyze the obtained results. We show the main properties of the proposed approach in terms of computational complexity, optimality, and feasibility, and how this approach outperforms a first-arrived first-served policy which optimizes vessels as they arrive to the waterway without modifying the trips of other vessels already sailing through it. Due to the discretization of the map of depth, units [$h/10$] and [$km/10$] are employed in all the simulation.

Figure 11: Optimization time; waiting and navigation costs.

Figures 10 and 11 show the effect of the number of vessels considered, N , on the complexity of the problem, the different costs, and the computing time. The results shown are the average values of 50 different scenarios for increasing values of N and fixed values of λ and D_L . The initial time of each scenario is chosen randomly in the first 24 hours of the week. In this set of scenarios, vessels arrive both at the port of Seville and the river estuary with a mean frequency of $\lambda = 3$ hours and have a maximum of $D_L = 18$ hours to reach their destination. In these simulations, the width of the different vessels has been randomly generated.

Figure 10 shows the number of binary variables, constraints and safe tubes. This figure shows that the number of binary variables and constraints grow polynomially with N , while the number of safe tubes is almost linear.

Figure 11 shows the computation time needed to solve the problem using Gurobi, and the waiting and navigation costs. This figure shows that the computation time grows exponentially as expected while the costs grow almost linearly. We notice that, even for a large number of vessels, the optimization problem is solved within a reasonable time. Note that, because the set of safe tubes can be computed in advance knowing the prediction of the time, this time has not been considered.

Figure 12 shows the effect of the maximum trip time D_L on the complexity of the problem in terms of the number of safe tubes for a total of 12 vessels, i.e., $N = 12$ and a fixed value of $\lambda = 3$ hours. As it can be seen, the number of safe tubes grows with D_L . In Table 2 we show the time it takes to compute these sets of safe tubes applying the procedure detailed by the flow diagram depicted in Figure 6 as a function of D_L . As it can be appreciated, computing time grows exponentially with the value of D_L . It is also interesting to see how, given the

Figure 12: Number of safe tubes with respect of D_L for a fixed value of t_i^{ready} .

periodic nature of the tide, the number of tubes generated strongly depends on t_i^{ready} . This is shown in Figures 13 and 14 for vessels sailing upstream and downstream, respectively. As it can be seen, both grow exponentially with D_L , but the number of tubes generated when sailing downstream is greater than the number of tubes generated when sailing upstream. This is because in the case of vessels sailing upstream, the only option is to surf the wave generated by the tide, while when sailing downstream the vessel may have to wait for the next tide to overcome some points of the waterway, and often this can be done in different times of the trip, leading to multiple options to arrive before the time limit $t_i^{ready} + D_L$.

Regarding waiting and navigation costs, it is important to see that these can be affected by the values of the waiting parameters α and β , for the navigation and waiting costs, respectively. To see the effect of these parameters on the costs included in the performance index, simulations have been carried out varying the value of α for a fixed value of β . In these simulations, the value of D_L has been fixed to 200 h/10, the number of vessels considered is $N = 6$, and the arrival frequency parameter has been fixed to $\lambda = 3$ hours. The results obtained are the mean values of a series of 100 randomly generated scenarios. These are shown in Table 3.

Choosing an appropriate value for D_L is important because if it is chosen too small, it may not be possible to reach the destination during that period, yielding and infeasible problem. To demonstrate this issue, we present a simulation in which 50 random scenarios are generated fixing $N = 12$ and $\lambda = 3$ hours for decreasing values of D_L . The results are shown in Table IV. For each value of

Figure 13: Number for tubes generated for vessels sailing upstream as a function of D_L and t_i^{ready} .

Table 3: Effect of the weighting parameters on waiting and navigation costs.

α	β	C_W	C_N
0.5	1	21.13	686.87
1	1	76.36	631.5
1.5	1	319.24	388.62
2	1	533.26	275.61
2.5	1	637.25	223.61

Table 4: Effect of D_L on the feasibility of the problem.

$D_L[h/1]$	150	160	170	180	190	200	210	220
% UF	100	86	50	6	0	0	0	0

D_L , the percentage of scenarios starting in an initial random time on the first 24 hours which are not feasible (% UF) are obtained. As expected, if D_L is too small, the vessels cannot reach their destination because no feasible tube can be found. It is important to remark that those vessels that need longer trip times are those travelling against the tide from the estuary of the river to the Port of Seville. These vessels need over 16 hours to ensure that a feasible tube will exist. Remember that the worst case scenario is considered, i.e, vessels of a draught equal to 7.5 meters.

We present next some experiments that demonstrate that using the proposed planning approach can improve the performance of the port. To this end,

Figure 14: Number for tubes generated for vessels sailing downstream as a function of D_L and t_i^{ready} .

Table 5: Effect of λ on the feasibility of the problem.

$\lambda[h/10]$	1	3	5	10	30	60	120
Large size							
% UF Baseline	100	100	100	100	100	0	0
% UF Proposed	100	31	0	0	0	0	0
Random size							
% UF Baseline	36	35	34	28	27	2	0
% UF Proposed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

the proposed approach is compared to the baseline solution in which in each scenario, vessels are scheduled individually as they arrive to the waterway. This is a first-arrived first-served (FA/FS) approach in which an operator schedules each vessel optimally considering the speed, depth, and width constraints while fixing the plan of the previous vessels. This first-arrived first-served approach does not profit from the possibility of planning all vessels simultaneously, leading to a worse performance as demonstrated in the results. The planning in the first-arrived first served approach is solved by fixing the values of the previously planned trips for vessels getting earlier to the waterway.

The first simulation demonstrates that, for an increasing frequency of vessel arrivals (λ), feasibility issues may arise if vessels are scheduled individually, which in real operation means that vessels inside the waterway may have to modify their previously decided plans. The results are shown in Table V, where

Table 6: Effect of λ on the cost of the problem comparing the costs of the proposed solution with those obtained when the first-arrived first-served (FA/FS) approach is adopted.

$\lambda[h/10]$	C_W FA/FS	C_W	C_N FA/FS	C_N	ΔC
3	201.45	16 0.99	615.33	612.94	42.84
5	230.34	188.18	617.55	624.86	34.84
10	245.12	208.93	595.34	599.27	32.26
30	240.41	206.27	577.58	582.21	29.51
60	200.84	253.62	628.23	555.83	19.62
120	50.32	155.93	733.98	628.37	0

the percentage of unfeasible scenarios using both the baseline and the proposed approach are shown (UF Baseline and UF Proposed, respectively). In these scenarios, $N = 8$, $D_L = 18$ hours and $t^{init} = 0$. We consider two different cases. In the first one, to account for the worst-case scenario, all vessels are large, i.e., $b(i) = 4$. In the second one, the size of the vessels is randomly selected. For each value of λ , 50 scenarios are generated randomly. It can be seen how the proposed approach is always better (not worse) than the first-arrived first-served approach.

After showing that the proposed approach outperforms the first-arrived first-served one in terms of feasibility, we show that the cost of the proposed solution is always better than the cost of the first-arrived first-served solution, thus reducing the total time vessels spend waiting and navigating through the waterway. Again, 50 random scenarios for $N = 8$ are generated fixing the initial time to some random value in the first 24 hours of the week, D_L to 18 hours and increasing the value of λ from 6 minutes to 1 hour. In this case, the size of all vessels is randomly selected. The results obtained are shown in Table VI. As it can be seen, the proposed solution outperforms the first-arrived first-served one in terms of cost and the difference between the cost of the first-arrived first-served solution and the proposed solution, ΔC , grows as λ decreases, i.e., as the frequency of vessels getting to the port increases.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we proposed a two-step optimization-based approach to schedule and plan vessels in a natural waterways with a time-varying depth, taking the time vessels cross through to each boundary dividing the waterway as decision variables. An algorithm is proposed to find the optimal windows in which vessels should cross each delimiting point to satisfy the depth constraint. We demonstrated by extensive simulation of different scenarios in the Guadalquivir river that the proposed formulation can be applied to solve the planning problem for a set of vessels and that the computational time is tractable even for a large number of vessels. It is shown that the solution of the proposed problem im-

proves the first-arrived first-served solution in terms of optimality and feasibility. In future works, the proposed solution will be developed as a management tool for the Port of Seville.

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